

PORTRAIT OF SHAYBANI CREATORS IN THE SOURCES OF THE 16TH CENTURY

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Annotation

16th century many history and tazkira works was created . During this period " Baburnama " by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur , " History " by Muh amm ad H ayd ar mirz o Rashidi " , Hasankhoja Nisari's " Muzakkiri". like " dude " . works was created . Them many creators row naughty pencil the owners also information about given _

Key words : historical source , art world , creator nature , skill , literary-critical views _

XV century and of the 16th century the first in half cultural life , science , art and architecture progressive did _ Especially astronomy , geography _ and medicine sciences high improvement achieved _ Dozens scientific works scientists by discover done _ From this except Herat , Bukhara , Samarkand and in Tashkent big-big architectural monuments , mosques and madrassas to this came _ In the country people of the farm recovery with one in line painting , music and artistic literature is also progressive reached went _

Proficiency of property the owner is Mir Alisher Navoi creativity product to be dozen works of the 15th century Uzbek of literature rare samples became _ As in the 16th century many history and tazkira works was created . To this example by doing " Baburnama " by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur , " History " by Muh amm ad H ayd ar mirz o Rashidi " , Hasankhoja Nisari's " Muzakkiri". like " dude " . his works show can _ Them many creators row naughty pencil the owners also information about given _ For example , in " Baburnoma". the author Shaibani Khan , his son Khurramshah about information cause past _ This data we critical evaluate our learning it is necessary Because Babur what about and who about Do n't write it is sincere . His own neither joy nor sorrow _ from whom don't hide it , honestly says _ A friend about the enemy about it _ speaks . That's right , enemies about When he wrote , sometimes pain cool from impartiality _ withdrawn places are also found . This his To Shaibani Khan gave critical in the price open to see can _ From history It is known that Shaibani Khan Babur's From Movarounnahr Entirely to go reason has been is a person . Har two of the person relationships in learning and their history complete in lighting historical sources carefully research reach must will be Mirza Babur's To Shaibani Khan has been to relations as for this event as acceptance to do must will be Babur To Shaibani Khan relatively hostility does not hide his attitude . His own higher goals hindrance did this person (Shaibani Khan) . only negative in paints describes , negative to the sides attention more looks _

So although - work author Muhammad Shaibani Khan about some in places positive that he also expressed his thoughts witness to be can _ Shaibani Khan one queue soz bidurur , takalluf even worse _ cholur , also own word do not bring , naughty soz brings _ Shaibani Khan understanding , I order , in the conversation-shoot victory to the neck hit _ Shaibani Khan's in

the world one good my dream there is that's it , cereal ok there is Spinach delicate to the heroes mundin the bridge tune need ", [1, 140] - like information meeting can _

The Shaybanites about " History" of Muh a mm a d H a yd a r mirz o in the work of Rashidi while some information giving passed . Including in the work the devils reign , marches about information meeting can _ For example , Muhammad Shaibani Khan negative from the features one as Muh a mm a d H a yd a r mirz o 's his father that he killed others of his own row to kill ordered about of the work ten fifth season " Book to the author concerned events statement " in [2,319]. passed . Shahibek Khan my father a martyr from doing after To Bukhara man sent to Khojand to the river drown those who did to the line to add for me to the river wants to leave it happened Although this command perform my sister husband Ubaidullah the sultan for heavy to deny it though _ in it in general possibility no was ". [2, 319] Hasankhoja Nisari's " Muzakkiri". Shaybani also in the work " Ahbob " . about valuable data given _ This work above from the works Shaybanites about of information wider to be given according to difference did _ " Muzakkiri "Ahbob " check the first column the first in the season important information meeting can _ For example , Shaybani of the dynasty founder Muhammad Shaibani Khan to the definition artistic from adjectives fruitful using price given , his rulership of activity to the beginning about prophetic events cause past : " And high school Khan Muhammad Shaibani Khan Amir Abdulali Tarkhan in the time Bukhara in the property quiet those who are Some hypocrite villains slander that person _ living own out of place out leave level delivered and then Khan sir master mischievous Bahauddin Naqshbandi's to the light full grave around Go , master destructive grandson - aliyjoh , hidayatpanoh Nizamiddin Khoja Mir Mohammad Naqshbandi services in honor of Musharraf was _ Tawaf and service in honor of after while to leave permission Those who asked , if it is Khoja Mir Muhammad , we will give you immediately answer those who say we will not give . From this after a little lifetime that's it to the light full grave next to those who are and exaggeration prayer on sale by reading those who walk One day Khoja Mir Muhammad said , " Ghayb keys his in front of it great Fatah own from the keys one the key enough in the palm of your hand to put it seems But this of work surface output Turkestan province on the sides happened will give And they are prophetic to the hint compliance after doing , almost ten two year during Turkestan from the region To the border of Domgan (Khorasan). lands own disposition to the circle enter , dorussaltana Herat and Samarkand itself Humayun to their horses sermon those who taught and honor is happiness on the throne happy those who killed " Tell me , hey." my God property the king you are him wanted from your person you can and wanted to the king you give " . [3, 19-20]

The author own by Muhammad Shaibani Khan virtue separately stopping at the potential high price from his work samples cause past _ " The host Khan knowledge is one of the virtues aware , more precisely , them full occupied person was _ Poetry field and to the poets belief-focus big was _ Good has poems . His Holiness sheikh Najmuddin Kubra - to him God thank you let it be - his death history good said _ History :

His is history shahi witness _

Another one alif together it will be fine.

I like this idea too to be said :

Sogd inside they kill they will

of Yubu rode horse they will

of Yubu He didn't stop long ago ,

Oh these are let it be this on the ground these are ". [3, 20]

Hasankhoja Nisari Shaybani turkish language laws good that he knows one the event to bring through separately emphasizing past _ " They say , hon Hazara the castle conquest when riding one ghazal It's over , Hiri Sheikhu Islam and Judge Optionally sent _ Here it is one how many byte that's it from the ghazal is ending . Byte:

Mandin Hello there ul Sheikh Ikhtiyorga ,
Na Ikhtiorkim , ul greedy , greedy .
God grace know people Hazara _
Andok Let's try it let it be please _

Judge Voluntary turkish the language don't know so , him for turkish language laws and regulations the book finished sent ." [3, 21]

Summary who does as for Shaybani dynasty own during separately place held _ Especially Shaibani _ rule did period social , political , cultural life to himself special way formed . These events " Baburnoma " by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur , Muhammad Haidar Mirza 's History Rashidi " , Hasankhoja Nisari's " Muzakkiri". akhbob " in his works differently interpretation done and in them of information each one important and is valuable .

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